

Sub-micrometer Sized, 3D-Surface-attached Polymer Networks by Microcontact Printing: Using UV-Crosslinking Efficiency to Tune Structure Height

Vania Tanda Widyaya,¹ Esther K. Riga,¹ Claas Müller,² and Karen Lienkamp^{1,}*

¹ Bioactive Polymer Synthesis and Surface Engineering Group, Department of Microsystems Engineering (IMTEK) and Freiburg Center for Interactive Materials and Bioinspired Technologies (FIT), Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Georges-Köhler-Allee 105, 79110 Freiburg, Germany

² Laboratory for Process Technology, Department of Microsystem Engineering (IMTEK), Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Georges-Köhler-Allee 103, 79110 Freiburg, Germany

*E-mail: lienkamp@imtek.uni-freiburg.de

ABSTRACT

The lateral dimensions of micro- and nanostructures obtained by microcontact printing (μ CP) can be easily varied by selecting stamps with the desired spacing and pattern. However, the height of these structures cannot be tuned as easily, and in most cases only 2D structures are obtained. Here, we show how the chemical cross-linking properties of polymer inks designed for μ CP can be used

to obtain 3D structures with heights ranging from 3 to 750 nm using the same μ CP stamps. This is technologically relevant because the ink concentration affects the quality and resolution of the printed image, and therefore can only be varied in a certain range. By exploiting the cross-linking efficiency to tune the height, an additional parameter is available to reach the desired structure height without compromising the image quality. The inks were made from copolymers containing a low percentage of different UV cross-linkable repeat units: nitrobenzoxadiazole (NBD), coumarin (COU), and/or benzophenone (BP). The base polymer of the here presented model system was an antimicrobially active poly(oxanorbornene) (Synthetic Mimic of Antimicrobial Peptides, SMAMP), however the concept should be transferable to many other polymer backbones. We describe the fabrication and characterization of the printed micro- and nanostructures made from pure SMAMP, NBD-SMAMP, coumarin-SMAMP, BP-SMAMP, BP-NBD-SMAMP and BP-coumarin-SMAMP polymer inks. The photo-dimerization of COU during UV irradiation at $\lambda = 254$ nm was confirmed by UV-Vis spectroscopy. Since NBD and COU are fluorescent, the polymer could be visualized by fluorescence microscopy. Additionally, their height profiles were measured by atomic force microscopy (AFM). The heights of the 3D surface-attached polymer networks obtained from the here presented polymer inks correlated with the gel-content and the degree of swelling of the corresponding unstructured polymer layers, and thus with the cross-linking efficiency of the NBD, COU and BP cross-linkers. Due to being covalently cross-linked, these 3D-surface attached polymer structures were solvent-stable and stable in aqueous surroundings.

INTRODUCTION

Microcontact printing (μ CP) is a straightforward and non-photolithographic technique for the preparation of structured surfaces with sub-micrometer resolution. Using this method, structured surfaces with topographic as well as chemical contrast can be obtained, depending on the inks selected for stamping.¹⁻⁵ Polymers have been used as inks for μ CP because they often strongly adhere to the contact area, and because their diffusivity and thus their tendency to migrate into a non-contact area is low.³ During the past years, impressive progress of 2D patterning with synthetic polymers⁶⁻⁹ and biological polymers (particularly proteins¹⁰⁻¹³ and DNA¹⁴⁻¹⁶) has been reported. However, 3D structuring using μ CP remains a major challenge. Potential applications of 3D micro- and nano-structured surfaces can be found in many scientifically and technologically important areas including water sanitization,¹⁷⁻¹⁸ microelectromechanical systems (MEMS),¹⁹⁻²¹ BioMEMS,²²⁻²⁴ robotics,²⁵ microfluidics,²⁶⁻²⁸ and sensors²⁹⁻³¹. Only a handful of studies on the fabrication of 3D polymeric microstructured surface using μ CP have been reported. Arrington et al. described the structuring of silicon wafers by μ CP using a PDMS stamps with a line pattern (spacing 25 μ m) and poly(amidoamine) (PAMAM) dendrimer inks, where the polymer had a molecular weight of about 14,000 g mol⁻¹. By tuning the concentration of the inks from 1 μ mol L⁻¹ to 1 mmol L⁻¹, the height of the resulting PAMAM structures could be varied from a monolayer to 60 nm high multilayers.³² Kohli et al. used silanized PAMAM-based dendrimers as inks, which could be cross-linked through their ethoxysilane moieties. Using dot and line stamps with 15-25 μ m spacing, they could show that thermally and hydrolytically stable features with heights up to 450 nm height could be obtained.³³ Na et al. used PEG-co-PMMA comb polymers (molecular weight 30,000 g mol⁻¹) as inks to print micro wells for cell culture, and obtained patterns height between 52 to 520 nm depending on the polymers concentration. These patterns had a 40 μ m

spacing and were stable in cell culture media due to the amphiphilic structure of the polymer, with the methacrylate backbone physisorbed onto the glass substrate.³⁴ Guan et al. reported the transfer of $30 \times 30 \mu\text{m}$ PMMA patches using μCP , which had a height of 620 nm.³⁵ In all these reports, the heights of the structures obtained were adjusted by varying the amount of material transferred during the stamping process, either via the ink concentration or the inking/stamping process parameters. With the exception of the report of Kohli,³³ all these 3D polymer structures were stabilized by physical forces, but not by chemical bonds. This gives a limitation of their robustness.

Herein, we report the fabrication of solvent and water-stable submicrometer-sized 3D polymer networks by microcontact printing using UV cross-linkable polymer inks. The stability of these structures is achieved by covalent bonds both to the substrate and between the polymer chains. Additionally, the height of the 3D surface features can be tuned by exploiting the different chemical properties of the different polymer inks used, namely the cross-linking efficiency of these polymers. This is a technologically important feature, because high quality μCP structures can typically only be obtained in a system-dependent concentration range (to avoid over and under-loading of the stamp), so that the height of the stamped features cannot be tuned without paying attention to printing quality considerations. By exploiting the cross-linking efficiency to tune the height, an additional parameter is available to reach the desired structure height without compromising the image quality. The polymer inks used herein were high molecular weight poly(oxanorbornenes) and contained different covalently bound UV-active chemical cross-linkers. They were stamped onto different substrates that had been functionalized with a benzophenone (BP) cross-linker for surface attachment.³⁶⁻³⁷ Upon UV irradiation, covalent bonds formed between the surface-attached BP groups and the polymer chains, and also between the different cross-linker units and neighboring polymer chains throughout the ink material, so that 3D, submicrometer-

sized surface-attached polymer networks were obtained (Figure 1). Benzophenone repeat units are well-established as highly efficient UV cross-linkers that undergo C-H insertion reactions upon irradiation with neighboring C-H bonds.³⁸⁻⁴⁰ We show in this paper that these repeat units efficiently stabilize even submicrometer-sized polymer networks. Coumarin derivatives (COU) readily undergo photo-dimerization under UV irradiation at $\lambda > 350$ nm, and reversibly undergo photo-cleavage when irradiated at $\lambda < 260$ nm.⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ In our system, we demonstrate that the photo-dimerization of coumarin also occurred at $\lambda = 254$ nm, however at this wavelength the cross-linking was less efficient than that of the corresponding BP polymer. NBD derivatives are commonly used as fluorophores,⁴⁵⁻⁴⁹ yet they have not yet been reported as cross-linkers (and admittedly do so less efficiently than BP or COU). Yet, using this low-efficiency cross-linker, more shallow microstructured 3D networks were accessible, as described below. Thus, exploiting the different chemical properties of these three cross-linking moieties, we present a set of μ CP inks that enabled us to make solvent and water-stable, submicrometer-sized 3D surface-attached polymer networks with heights ranging from thin monolayers to 750 nm.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

General. All chemicals and solvents (reagent grade) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Munich, Germany) or Carl Roth (Karlsruhe, Germany) and used as received unless otherwise stated. Dichloromethane (DCM) for polymer synthesis was distilled over CaH_2 under nitrogen gas. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker 250 MHz spectrometer (Bruker, Madison, WI, USA). Gel permeation chromatography (GPC) was measured using PSS column (Mainz, Germany) and calibrated against PMMA standards. For all SMAMP (Synthetic Mimic of Antimicrobial Peptides)

polymer and copolymers, chloroform HPLC grade was used as eluent. Coumarin homopolymer was measured using DMF as eluent. Single-side polished silicon wafers with [100] orientation and $525 \pm 25 \mu\text{m}$ thickness were obtained from Si-Mat (Kaufering, Germany). Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) stamps having cosine wave patterns with $2 \mu\text{m}$ and $1 \mu\text{m}$ spacing (Figure S1 in the Supporting Information) were cut into $2 \times 1.5 \text{ cm}^2$ pieces. In short, the patterned silicon master ($15 \times 15 \text{ cm}^2$) used to make these stamps was fabricated using Laser Interference Lithography. Then, PDMS solution (Elastosil® RT601, Wacker Chemie AG, Stuttgart, Germany) was poured onto the Si master and molded. Spin-coating was performed on a SPIN150-NPP (SPS-Europe, Putten, Netherlands). The UV irradiation unit used was a BIO-LINK-box (Vilber Lourmat GmbH, Eberhardzell, Germany) with 254 nm and 365 nm light source.

Polymers Synthesis. The synthesis of the Boc-protected propyl-SMAMP monomer,⁵⁰ NBD monomer,⁵¹ coumarin monomer,⁵¹ and BP monomer⁵² are described elsewhere. Grubbs' 3rd generation catalyst (G3) was also synthesized as previously reported.⁵³ They were polymerized by ring-opening metathesis polymerization (ROMP) at room temperature under nitrogen using standard Schlenk techniques. SMAMP monomer (500 mg, 1.4 mmol) was dissolved in 4 mL of dry DCM. The G3 catalyst solution (3.6 mg in 1 mL of dry DCM, 5 μmol) was added in one shot into the stirred monomer solution. After 1 h, excess ethyl vinyl ether (1 mL, 10 mmol) was added to terminate the ROMP reaction and the mixture was stirred for another 1 h. DCM was then evaporated under reduced pressure. The product was re-dissolved in small amount of DCM and precipitated into ice-cooled *n*-hexane. The precipitated polymer was filtered and dried under high vacuum. The SMAMP copolymers were synthesized in the same manner with monomer compositions listed in Table 1. Coumarin homopolymer was synthesized by the same procedure as the SMAMP polymer, except that 10 mL of dry DCM was needed to dissolve 500 mg of

coumarin monomer. The chemical structure of the polymers can be seen in Figure 1 and Figure 5b.

Table 1. Monomer and G3 catalyst composition for polymer synthesis. The resulting polymer listed in this table are the moieties copolymerized with SMAMP. COU = coumarin. The molecular weight (M_n , kg mol⁻¹) and polydispersity index (PDI) of the polymers are also listed.

Polymers	Monomer composition & added G3 catalyst	M_n (kg mol ⁻¹)	PDI
1	500 mg, 1.4 mmol SMAMP; 3.6 mg, 5 μ mol G3	94	1.1
2 (NBD)	500 mg, 1.4 mmol, 9 eq SMAMP; 55.9 mg, 0.15 mmol, 1 eq NBD; 4 mg, 5.5 μ mol G3	75	1.3
3 (COU)	500 mg, 1.4 mmol, 9 eq SMAMP; 53.1 mg, 0.15 mmol, 1 eq COU; 4 mg, 5.5 μ mol G3	87	1.1
4 (BP)	500 mg, 1.4 mmol, 9 eq SMAMP; 58.6 mg, 0.15 mmol, 1 eq BP; 4 mg, 5.5 μ mol G3	90	1.1
5 (BP-NBD)	500 mg, 1.4 mmol, 8 eq SMAMP; 65.8 mg, 0.17 mmol, 1 eq BP; 62.8 mg, 0.17 mmol, 1 eq NBD; 4.5 mg, 6.3 μ mol G3	92	1.2
6 (BP-COU)	500 mg, 1.4 mmol, 8 eq SMAMP; 65.8 mg, 0.17 mmol, 1 eq BP; 59.8 mg, 0.17 mmol, 1 eq COU; 4.5 mg, 6.3 μ mol G3	91	1.1
7 (COU)	500 mg, 1.4 mmol COU; 3.6 mg, 5 μ mol G3	108	1.4

The ¹H NMR signals (250 MHz, in CDCl₃ unless otherwise stated, δ / ppm) of the resulting SMAMP (co)polymers are as follows (see Figure 1 and Figure 5b for the chemical structure of the polymers):

SMAMP (**1**): 5.92 (br s, 1H, 1-t), 5.62 (br s, 1H, 9), 5.42 (br s, 1H, 1-c), 5.14 (br s, 1H, 2-c), 4.72 (br s, 1H, 2-t), 4.17 (br s, 2H, 7), 4.09 (br s, 2H, 4), 3.38 (br s, 2H, 8), 3.15 (br s, 2H, 3 & 3'), 1.65 (m, 2H, 5), 1.46 (s, 9H, 10, 10', & 10''), 0.95 (s, 3H, 6).

NBD-SMAMP (**2**): 8.53 (s, 1H, 14), 6.26 (s, 1H, 13), 5.92 (br s, 1H, 1-t), 5.62 (br s, 1H, 9), 5.42 (br s, 1H, 1-c), 5.14 (br s, 1H, 2-c), 4.72 (br s, 1H, 2-t), 4.17 (br s, 2H, 7), 4.09 (br s, 2H, 4), 3.38 (br s, 2H, 8), 3.15 (br s, 2H, 3 & 3'), 1.65 (m, 2H, 5), 1.46 (s, 9H, 10, 10', & 10''), 0.95 (s, 3H, 6).

COU-SMAMP (**3**): 7.69 (br s, 1H, 16), 7.43 (br s, 1H, 15), 6.83 (br s, 2H, 13 & 17), 6.29 (br s, 1H, 14), 5.92 (br s, 1H, 1-t), 5.62 (br s, 1H, 9), 5.42 (br s, 1H, 1-c), 5.14 (br s, 1H, 2-c), 4.72 (br s, 1H, 2-t), 4.17 (br s, 2H, 7), 4.09 (br s, 2H, 4), 3.38 (br s, 2H, 8), 3.15 (br s, 2H, 3 & 3'), 1.65 (m, 2H, 5), 1.46 (s, 9H, 10, 10', & 10''), 0.95 (s, 3H, 6).

BP-SMAMP (**4**): 6.96 – 7.85 (m, 9H, 13-21), 5.92 (br s, 1H, 1-t), 5.62 (br s, 1H, 9), 5.42 (br s, 1H, 1-c), 5.14 (br s, 1H, 2-c), 4.72 (br s, 1H, 2-t), 4.17 (br s, 2H, 7), 4.09 (br s, 2H, 4), 3.38 (br s, 2H, 8), 3.15 (br s, 2H, 3 & 3'), 1.65 (m, 2H, 5), 1.46 (s, 9H, 10, 10', & 10''), 0.95 (s, 3H, 6).

BP-NBD-SMAMP (**5**): 8.53 (s, 1H, 23), 6.96 – 7.85 (m, 9H, 13-21), 6.26 (s, 1H, 22), 5.92 (br s, 1H, 1-t), 5.62 (br s, 1H, 9), 5.42 (br s, 1H, 1-c), 5.14 (br s, 1H, 2-c), 4.72 (br s, 1H, 2-t), 4.17 (br s, 2H, 7), 4.09 (br s, 2H, 4), 3.38 (br s, 2H, 8), 3.15 (br s, 2H, 3 & 3'), 1.65 (m, 2H, 5), 1.46 (s, 9H, 10, 10', & 10''), 0.95 (s, 3H, 6).

BP-COU-SMAMP (**6**): 6.96 – 7.85 (m, 9H, 13-21, overlapping with COU peaks: br s, 2H, 24 & 25), 6.83 (br s, 2H, 22 & 26), 6.29 (br s, 1H, 23), 5.92 (br s, 1H, 1-t), 5.62 (br s, 1H, 9), 5.42 (br s, 1H, 1-c), 5.14 (br s, 1H, 2-c), 4.72 (br s, 1H, 2-t), 4.17 (br s, 2H, 7), 4.09 (br s, 2H, 4), 3.38 (br s, 2H, 8), 3.15 (br s, 2H, 3 & 3'), 1.65 (m, 2H, 5), 1.46 (s, 9H, 10, 10', & 10''), 0.95 (s, 3H, 6).

COU homopolymer (**7**, in DMSO-d₆): 7.91 (br s, 1H, 9), 7.51 (br s, 1H, 8), 6.97 (br s, 1H, 6), 6.88 (br s, 1H, 10), 6.25 (br s, 1H, 7), 5.93 (br s, 1H, 1-t), 5.77 (br s, 1H, 1-c), 4.9 (br s, 2H, 2-t & 2-c), 4.2-4.35 (br m, 2H, 4), 3.76 (br s, 2H, 3 & 3'), 3.44 (br s, 2H, 5).

Microcontact Printing. All steps of the μ CP process were performed under ambient conditions.

Surface silanization. The silanization agent triethoxy benzophenone silane (3EBP-silane) was synthesized as described in the literature.³⁶ A solution of 3EBP-silane (20 mg mL⁻¹ in toluene) was spin-coated (3000 rpm, 1000 rpm s⁻¹, 30 s) onto a silicon wafer. The wafer was then cured at 120°C for 20 min on a preheated hotplate and washed with toluene. It was then cut into 1.5 × 1.5 cm²

pieces. *Ink pad preparation.* SMAMP (co)polymer (2 mg for inking the 2 μm spacing stamp; 5 mg for the 1 μm spacing stamp) was dissolved in 1 mL of a mixture of 30% v/v DCM and 70% v/v toluene. The polymer solution (0.05 mL) was then spin-coated (150 rpm, 150 rpm s⁻¹, 5 s) onto a microscope slide (2.5 \times 2.5 \times 0.1 cm³, VWR, Germany). *Surface structuring with μCP .* PDMS stamps were loaded with SMAMP ink by placing the stamp on the ink pad for 5 s and allowing it to dry for 10 s. The ink-loaded stamp was brought into conformal contact with the substrate and pressed onto it with a pressure of about 30 N for 5 s. The thus patterned surfaces were then UV-irradiated ($\lambda = 254$ nm, energy 3 J cm⁻²). Any loosely attached SMAMP ink was rinsed off by immersing the surface in stirred toluene for 18 h. The sample was then dried under nitrogen flow.

Unstructured polymer films. *Gel content.* Unstructured polymer samples were prepared by spin coating polymer solution (20 mg mL⁻¹ in 30% v/v DCM - 70% v/v toluene, spin coater: 3000 rpm, 1000 rpm s⁻¹, 30 s) on silanized Si wafers, followed by UV irradiation ($\lambda = 254$ nm and/or $\lambda = 365$ nm, energy 3 J cm⁻²). The initial film thickness was measured by ellipsometry (see below). After the initial film thickness was measured, loose polymer chains were removed by immersion into stirred toluene for 18 h. The surface was then dried under nitrogen flow and the layer thickness was again measured using ellipsometry. The gel content g of the cross-linked polymer was obtained as the ratio of the thickness of extracted polymer film h and the thickness of initially deposited film h_0 : $g = h / h_0$. *Degree of swelling (DS).* Swelling experiment was conducted using surface plasmon resonance (SPR) spectroscopy (see below). First, SPR substrates were functionalized with anchor group lipoic acid benzophenone (LS-BP, 10 mg mL⁻¹ in toluene, synthesized as described in the literature³⁷) by immersing the SPR substrates in LS-BP solution for 12 h. The substrates were then rinsed with toluene and dried under nitrogen flow. Polymer solution was deposited onto the SPR substrate by spin coating (40 mg mL⁻¹ in 30% v/v DCM -

70% v/v toluene, spin coater: 1000 rpm, 1000 rpm s⁻¹, 10 s), followed by UV irradiation ($\lambda = 254$ nm, energy 3 J cm⁻²). Loosely attached polymer chains were removed by immersion into stirred methanol for 18 h and the substrates were then dried under nitrogen flow. For NBD-SMAMP polymer network, it was necessary to coat the SPR substrate with negative permanent Epoxy Photoresin SU-8 2000.5 (MicroChem-Micro Resist Technology, Berlin, Germany) before NBD-SMAMP immobilization in order to obtain waveguide mode in SPR measurement. The SU-8 was spin coated onto the SPR substrate (500 rpm, 100 rpm s⁻¹, 10 s followed by 2000 rpm, 300 rpm s⁻¹, 30 s) and was immediately baked at 95°C for 1 min, followed by UV irradiation ($\lambda = 365$ nm, energy 80 mJ cm⁻²). Then, it was baked again at 95°C for 2 min. The substrate was let to cool down and rinsed with Developer mr-Dev 600 (Micro Resist Technology, Berlin, Germany) to remove non-cross-linked SU-8, followed by rinsing with isopropanol. Finally, the substrate was baked at 150°C for 5 min. The resin coated SPR substrate was functionalized with 3EBP-silane (procedure as described above) before NBD-SMAMP polymer solution was deposited onto it. In the swelling experiment, the polymer network was first covered with methanol for 10 min and then dried under constant nitrogen flow. SPR reflectivity curve was recorded until the polymer network was completely dried (indicated by a constant plasmon and waveguide mode position). Then, methanol was flowed into the flow cell again (20 μ l min⁻¹) and SPR reflectivity curve was recorded until complete swelling. The obtained curve was simulated with Fresnel calculations where the thickness d and the real permittivity ϵ' of the polymer network were obtained by fitting the calculated curve to match the plasmon minimum and the waveguide mode minimum. DS was calculated as: $DS = d_{solvent} / d_{dry}$.

Surface Characterization. *Fluorescence Microscopy.* Fluorescence microscopy images were taken using a Nikon Eclipse Ti-S inverted microscope (Nikon GmbH, Düsseldorf, Germany) with

a green-fluorescent-protein and a DAPI filter at 60-fold magnification. Imaging time was varied between 80 – 600 ms for green ink, and 1 – 4 s for blue ink. The images were processed using ImageJ. Brightness and image contrast were adjusted for better visualization. *Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM)*. Topography images were recorded in ScanAsyst tapping mode in air using a Dimension Icon AFM (Bruker, Karlsruhe, Germany). Commercial ScanAsyst Air cantilevers (length: 115 μm ; width: 25 μm ; spring constant: 0.4 N m^{-1} ; resonance frequency: 70 kHz) were used. All AFM images were analyzed and processed using Nanoscope Analysis 1.5. The baseline of the height profile images were vertically translated to zero position using OriginPro 2015G. *Ellipsometry*. The polymer layer thickness (and thus the gel content) was measured using the autonulling imaging ellipsometer Nanofilm EP3 (Nanofilm Technology GmbH, Göttingen, Germany). A refractive index of 1.5 was assumed for all measurements. The data was fitted using the EP4 model. Average values were obtained from six different positions on two sample surfaces. *UV-Vis Spectroscopy*. UV-Vis spectra of the COU polymer film cast on quartz glass was recorded using a Cary 50 Bio (Varian, USA). *Surface plasmon resonance (SPR) spectroscopy* (and thus the degree of swelling, DS) was measured using RT2005 RES-TEC in Kretschmann configuration (Res-Tec, Framersheim, Germany) with He-Ne laser ($\lambda = 632.8 \text{ nm}$). SPR substrates were made by Clean Room Service-Center (RSC) of the Department of Microsystem Engineering, University of Freiburg, using CS 730 S device (Von Ardenne, Dresden, Germany). In short, LaSFN9 glass (Hellma GmbH, Müllheim, Germany) was coated with 1 nm of Cr and 50 nm of Au.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We here present a series of polymer inks for microcontact printing (μ CP), where the specific chemical properties of the inks could be used to tune the heights of the 3D-structured surface features obtained. These polymer inks each contained a small fraction of different UV-active chemical cross-linkers (nitrobenzoxadiazole (NBD), coumarin (COU), benzophenone (BP), or a combination of these moieties, Figure 1), which were covalently attached to oxonorbornene imide repeat units. These repeat units were part of an amphiphilic poly(oxonorbornene diester) with antimicrobial activity (a so called Synthetic Mimic of Antimicrobial Peptides, SMAMPs).^{50, 54-55} The SMAMP polymer was chosen as base polymer for this study since the resulting antimicrobial 3D-surface structures were designed to investigate the interaction between bacteria and microstructured antimicrobial surfaces. However, due to the unspecificity of the reactivity of BP, which can cross-link with most aliphatic CH groups, and the fact that COU cross-links by dimerizing, the here presented concept should be transferable to many other polymers carrying BP, COU and NBD groups. A cartoon illustration of the target system is shown in Figure 1. The substrate onto which the inks were stamped was gold, glass, or silicon that had been chemically modified with either the UV cross-linker triethoxy benzophenone silane (3EBP-silane, for substrates with OH groups) or benzophenone attached to a lipoic acid disulfide (LS-BP, for gold) following literature procedures.³⁶⁻³⁷ Upon UV irradiation, covalent bonds formed between the surface-attached BP groups (orange dots in Figure 1) and the polymer chains, and also between the different polymer chains throughout the stamped pattern (red dots in Figure 1, representing generic cross-linking units). As a result, 3D submicrometer-sized surface-attached polymer networks were obtained. The microcontact printing process by which the here presented structures were obtained is shown in Figure 2. To load the stamp with ink, an ink pad was prepared by spin-coating a thin layer of polymer onto a microscope slide (Figure 2a, green layer). The PDMS stamp

was then placed onto the ink pad. This stamp loading procedure was advantageous over directly dipping the stamp into the ink solution as it prevented swelling, helped to localize the ink molecules on protruding areas of the stamp, and reduced the ink diffusion during stamping.⁵⁶⁻⁵⁷

Figure 1. Sub-micrometer sized, 3D surface-attached polymer networks (brown) were obtained by microcontact printing using different polymer inks (1 to 6). Besides the base polymer (SMAMP, 1), three copolymers (2-4) and two terpolymers (5 and 6) containing the cross-linker units benzophenone (BP, orange), nitrobenzoxadiazole (NBD, green), and coumarin (COU, blue) were used. Upon UV irradiation, these polymers were covalently bound to the BP-functionalized substrate (orange dots) and formed structured surface-attached polymer networks by inter-chain cross-linking (brown, red dots = generic cross-linker unit). The numbering of atoms of the polymers refers to ¹H NMR peak assignments in the Experimental Section.

The substrate was in most cases a Si wafer surface onto which 3EBP silane had been spin-coated. Upon curing at 120°C, the ethoxy groups of the 3EBP-silane formed a covalent bond with the OH groups of the native oxide layer on the Si substrate (orange layer in Figure 2b). Afterwards, the ink-loaded PDMS stamp was brought into conformal contact with the benzophenone-modified surface (Figure 2c). After removal of the stamp, the transferred surface features were UV-irradiated. Thus, all polymers were covalently attached to the substrate (Figure 2c). Any loosely attached polymers chain were then removed by immersion of the surface in stirred toluene for 18 h.

Figure 2. Cartoon illustration (not drawn to scale) of the μ CP process: a) A PDMS stamp (light blue) was loaded with an ink, e.g. NBD-SMAMP (green), via an ink pad. b) The target substrate had been previously functionalized with a layer of the 3EBP anchor group (orange). c) The ink was transferred when the stamp was brought into conformal contact with the 3EBP functionalized surface, giving highly resolved surface structures. The structures containing either NBD or COU: d) NBD-SMAMP & e) COU-SMAMP could be visualized by fluorescence microscopy.

Figure 3. AFM topography images and height profiles (diagonal section) of surface-attached monolayers and polymer networks. The structures were obtained by μ CP using a PDMS stamp with 2 μ m spacing, and polymers **1** to **6** as inks. Avg = average. The width at the base of each structure (diagonal section) was 1.5-1.6 μ m (**1**), 1.6-1.8 μ m (**2** and **3**), and 1.8-1.9 μ m (**4** to **6**).

Depending on the cross-linker units along the chains of polymers **1** to **6**, and on the cross-linking efficiency of these units, surface features with different heights were obtained by the μ CP process (all other parameters i.e. μ CP parameters, ink concentration, irradiation time, etc. were kept constant so that the different heights was solely depending on cross-linking efficiency). This was studied by atomic force microscopy (AFM) and is illustrated in Figure 3 for the features obtained from a 2 μ m spacing-PDMS stamp. For the SMAMP base polymer **1**, which contained no cross-linker, a surface-attached polymer monolayer with a thickness of 3 ± 2 nm was received (Figure 3a). Polymer **2**, which contained 10 mol% NBD, surprisingly gave features that were 80 ± 20 nm high (Figure 3b). (Originally, the NBD and COU groups had been chosen as functional groups for these polymers because they are fluorescent and thus enabled visualization of the surface structures by fluorescence microscopy (Figure 2d and 2e, respectively), and not because any cross-linking was expected.) Yet using polymer **3** containing 10 mol% of the blue-fluorescent COU groups, the feature size of the structures obtained was even 185 ± 45 nm (Figure 3c). This is only slightly shorter than the surface features obtained from polymer **4** (240 ± 50 nm, Figure 3d), which contained 10 mol% of the well-known BP crosslinker. When either BP/NBD or BP/COU were combined in the same polymer, the features sized obtained was even higher (750 ± 250 nm, Figure 3e and 3f). This data shows that both NBD and COU cross-link upon UV irradiation at $\lambda = 254$ nm. While coumarin cross-linking at $\lambda > 350$ nm is reported, we did not expect it to dimerize at 254 nm since it is known to undergo photo-cleavage at wavelengths below 260 nm.⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ Likewise, NBD has not yet been described as a potential crosslinker. Our hypothesis is that the electron-withdrawing NO₂ group of NBD reacted with the electron-rich double bond of the polymer backbone through IEDDA (Inverse Electron Demand Diels-Alder) pathways. This cycloaddition

process has been studied by Hallé et al.⁵⁸ where DNBF (4,6-dinitrobenzofuroxan) was reacted with ethyl vinyl ether (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. a) IEDDA reaction between DNBF and ethyl vinyl ether as reported by Hallé et al.⁵⁸ (re-draw with permission^[v11]). b) Hypothesis of crosslinking mechanism between NBD and double bond of polymer chain backbone through IEDDA pathways as explained by Hallé et al.⁵⁸

To rate the relative cross-linking efficiency of NBD, COU and BP crosslinkers, we made unstructured surface-attached polymer layers (initial thickness = 105 ± 1 nm for SMAMP, NBD-SMAMP, COU-SMAMP, and BP-SMAMP; 230 ± 5 nm for BP-NBD-SMAMP and BP-COU-SMAMP) from the polymers ink **1** to **6**, and determined the gel content of each layer. For this, a solution of each polymer ink was spin-coated onto a substrate that had been functionalized with 3EBP silane. After that, the substrate was UV-irradiated using the same conditions as for the structured surfaces ($\lambda = 254$ nm, overall irradiation energy 3 J cm^{-2}). The layer thickness of the

thus obtained coatings was measured by ellipsometry to determine the initial thickness. They were then washed with toluene to remove any loose polymer chains (i.e. the sol). After drying, the layer thickness of the remaining polymer (i.e. the gel) was measured by ellipsometry. From the ratio of the gel thickness and the initial thickness (sol+gel), the gel content of the network was obtained (Table 2). A plot of the gel content of the unstructured polymer layers versus the height of the 3D surface structures made from the same polymer (Figure 3) is shown in Figure 5a for all polymers. Polymers **2**, **3** and **4** each had 10 mol% of cross-linkable repeat units, while polymers **5** and **6** had 20 mol% cross-linkers. Therefore, the absolute structure height was also normalized by the cross-linker percentage of each polymer (Figure 5a, inset). Using this normalization, the correlation between the 3D structure height and the relative cross-linking efficiency of the respective cross-linkers (i.e. the gel content) is evident. Care has to be taken not to over-interpret this data quantitatively, yet the trends observed are clear. The data is also in line with recent work on unstructured surface-attached polymer network, where an efficiency factor was introduced to model the gel content of these networks using percolation theory.³⁹

Furthermore, in order to confirm the cross-linking efficiency of the three main crosslinkers (NBD, COU, and BP), the swelling behavior of the related SMAMP copolymers (after irradiated at $\lambda = 254$ nm, energy 3 J cm^{-2}) in methanol was studied with surface plasmon resonance (SPR) spectroscopy, and the results is listed in Table 2. In this experiment, the dry thickness of each SMAMP copolymer network, as well as their thickness under swollen condition in methanol, was measured. Then, the degree of swelling (DS) was calculated by dividing the thickness in swollen state with the dry thickness. As expected, the least efficient cross-linker, i.e. NBD, swelled the most (DS = 9.6), followed by COU and BP (DS = 3.2 and 1.8, respectively). This results showed that NBD, which had the lowest cross-link density, could penetrate into the solvent and swell better

than COU and BP did.⁵⁹ Thus, it could be concluded that the results from gel content test and degree of swelling are in agreement. The SPR reflectivity curves of swelling experiment can be seen in Figure S2 in the Supporting Information.

To check if the cross-linking process was wavelength-dependent, the gel content for the NBD-SMAMP (2) and the COU-SMAMP (3) was determined at $\lambda = 365$ nm, also with an overall energy of 3 J cm^{-2} . The data is also included in Table 2. In the case of the NBD-SMAMP (2), the gel content after this treatment was 2%, which corresponded to the gel content of a SMAMP (1) monolayer, i.e. no cross-linking was observed at $\lambda = 365$ nm for this polymer. For the COU-SMAMP (3), on the other hand, the gel content at $\lambda = 254$ nm was 70%, and increased to 89% for $\lambda = 365$ nm.

Figure 5. a) Gel content of unstructured surface-attached polymer networks vs. structure height and normalized structure height (inset) of 3D surface features obtained by μ CP; b) UV-Vis spectra of an unstructured COU homopolymer (7) film before UV irradiation (black curve), after irradiation at $\lambda = 254$ nm/ 3 J cm^{-2} (dark grey curve), and after further irradiation at $\lambda = 365$ nm/ 3 J cm^{-2} (light grey curve). The numbering of atoms of the COU homopolymer refers to ¹H NMR peak assignments in the Experimental Section.

Table 2. Gel content (%) and degree of swelling (DS, in methanol) of SMAMP homopolymer and copolymers after UV irradiation at $\lambda = 254$ nm and $\lambda = 365$ nm, respectively. The irradiation energy was 3 J cm^{-2} in each case.

	Irradiation wavelength	1	2 (NBD)	3 (COU)	4 (BP)	5 (BP-NBD)	6 (BP-COU)
Gel content (%)	$\lambda = 254$ nm	2	19	70	88	100	100
	$\lambda = 365$ nm	n.a	2	89	n.a	n.a	n.a
Degree of swelling	$\lambda = 254$ nm	n.a	9.6	3.2	1.8	n.a	n.a

This is in line with the literature reports that COU cross-linking is very efficient at wavelengths above 350 nm.⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ To find out why our COU system also cross-linked at 254 nm, we measured the UV-Vis spectra of a COU homopolymer (**7**) film that was cast on quartz glass. (COU-SMAMP (**3**) could not be used for this study because the UV adsorption band for that polymer was too weak.) Three situations were compared: the native film, the film irradiated at 254 nm (3 J cm^{-2}), and the film first irradiated at 254 nm (3 J cm^{-2}) and then at 365 nm (3 J cm^{-2}) (Figure 5b). As this data shows, COU has two absorption bands: the weak $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition from the benzene ring with $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 290$ nm, and the strong $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition corresponding to the C=C bond of 2-pyrone ring with $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 324$ nm. Photo-dimerization causes an intensity decrease of that band, as a $[2\pi + 2\pi]$ cycloaddition between two adjacent 2-pyrone rings consumes C=C bonds.^{41,43} Indeed, Figure 5b (dark grey curve) confirms that the absorbance at $\lambda = 324$ nm decreased after UV irradiation at $\lambda = 254$ nm, and thus the $[2\pi + 2\pi]$ cycloaddition also took place at that wavelength in our system. Further exposure at $\lambda = 365$ nm lowered the intensity of the $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition even more, as the photo-dimerization is more efficient at that wavelength. These results are consistent with the lower gel content of the COU-SMAMP polymer when irradiated at 254 nm than when irradiated at 365 nm (Table 2). We speculate that at $\lambda = 254$ nm, photo-dimerization and dimer photo-cleavage

occur simultaneously, but with different rates: the photo-cleavage should be much slower than the photo-dimerization at that wavelength, so that a gel content of 70% is obtained in the unstructured COU-SMAMP film. Besides the above described structures with 2 μm spacing, 3D surface-attached polymer features with 1 μm spacing were also fabricated using the NBD-SMAMP (2) and the BP-NBD-SMAMP (5) polymer inks. AFM topography images of these structures are shown in Figure 6, in direct comparison to the corresponding 2 μm structures. For the 1 μm structures, lower heights were obtained than for the corresponding 2 μm structures. Apparently, less ink was transferred with the 1 μm stamp than with the 2 μm stamp. For either ink, the 3D-structured surfaces obtained were stable in aqueous environments and in solvents. For example, the pattern was not re-dissolved even after 18 h immersion in stirred toluene.

Figure 6. AFM topography images of 3D-surface attached polymer features obtained by μCP using PDMS stamps with 1 μm and 2 μm spacing. Features were printed on 3EBP-functionalized Si wafers. The cartoons illustrate the spacing and height of the features (not drawn to scale, orange = BP layer, green = NBD ink, Avg = average).

CONCLUSIONS

In this work we described a series of six different poly(oxonorbornene) inks for microcontact printing (μ CP), and how the different efficiencies of the cross-linking moieties in these inks were used to tune the height of the 3D, submicrometer-sized surface-attached polymer networks thus obtained. The surfaces were fabricated using standard μ CP methods: the different polymer inks were stamped on surface functionalized with benzophenone groups, and then cross-linked and simultaneously surface-attached by UV irradiation. The thus obtained 3D structures were stable in solvent and in aqueous conditions.

Surprisingly, we found that the functional groups nitrobenzoxadiazole (NBD) and coumarin (COU), which are fluorescent and were originally included to visualize the surface structures, also cross-linked the base polymer when UV-irradiated at $\lambda = 254$ nm. This has not been reported for COU before, which is known to photo-dimerize at $\lambda > 350$ nm and photo-cleave at $\lambda < 260$ nm. Also, NBD has not yet been described as a photo-crosslinker. By UV-Vis spectroscopy, we could show that irradiation of an unstructured surface-attached COU homopolymer film at $\lambda = 254$ nm indeed caused photo-dimerization, although this process was more efficient at $\lambda = 365$ nm. For NBD, on the other hand, irradiation at $\lambda = 365$ nm did not induce crosslinking. So far, we do not have any structural evidence for the reaction causing NBD cross-linking, but suspect that Inverse Electron Demand Diels-Alder (IEDDA) reaction took place between the NO_2 group of NBD with the double bond of the polymer backbone.

Using unstructured surface-attached polymer networks made from the same polymers as the 3D structures, we could show that the gel content and the degree of swelling of the unstructured networks correlated with the height of the 3D structures. Thus, the relative efficiency of the cross-

linker systems here investigated was the same for unstructured networks and 3D structures, and of the order $NBD < COU < BP < BP/NBD \approx BP/COU$. Thus, besides the reported factors (polymer concentration, deposition conditions), we could show that the cross-linking efficiency can be used to tune the height of submicrometer sized, surface-attached 3D polymer networks. These findings are not limited to the here presented poly(oxonorborene) system, but should be transferable to other polymers that carry one of the three cross-linkers NBD, COU or BP.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images of the PDMS stamps and SPR reflectivity curves of swelling experiment are included in Supporting Information.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

E-mail: lienkamp@imtek.uni-freiburg.de

ORCID

Karen Lienkamp 0000-0001-6868-3707

Author Contributions

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